
231. Dwarf spheroidals: an update

I DESCRIBED the early Gaia results on dwarf spheroidal galaxies, based on DR2, in essay 31 (Aug 2021), and the Sagittarius stream specifically in essay 198. Before outlining the new insights from EDR3/DR3, let me summarise what they are, and what we learned from DR2.

The ‘classical’ dwarf spheroidal galaxies, or dSph, are small, low-luminosity galaxies comprising an old stellar population with very little dust (the ultra-faint dwarfs are even fainter!). In contrast to dwarf *elliptical* galaxies, they are roughly spheroidal in shape. Some two dozen are known as companions to either the Milky Way or to the Andromeda Galaxy (M31), and they are named after the constellation in which they are found.

The first known, Sculptor and Fornax, were discovered by Harlow Shapley in 1938, who described them as *‘unlike any known stellar organisation’*. But despite masses around $10^7 M_\odot$, further discoveries were challenged by their low luminosities and surface brightnesses. By the late 1990s, their rarity seemed in conflict with Λ CDM cosmology, which predicted that massive galaxies like the Milky Way should be surrounded by many dark-matter-dominated satellite halos.

CONFLICT eased with the discovery of a dozen faint dwarf spheroidals by SDSS around 2000, and a similar number by the Dark Energy Survey around 2015. The distinction between dwarf spheroidals and globular clusters is, incidentally, not always sharp: one discriminant may be the presence of a significant amount of dark matter in the former, and its absence in the latter.

All these dwarf galaxies are very distant, ranging from 26 kpc for Sagittarius, to around 250 kpc in the case of Leo I, well beyond the Magellanic Clouds. Their bulk proper motions are consequently very small, generally below 0.5 milli-arcsec per year. Some pre-Gaia determinations of these tiny motions were made using HST.

One main line of study is to use the Gaia data to reconstruct their orbits, structure, and internal dynamics. The goal is to characterise the gravitational forces of the galaxy that they are orbiting, either the Milky Way or M31, at larger distances than any other available dynamical tracer, and to probe their origin and past history.

THE MAIN INSIGHTS from Gaia DR2 came from an analysis by Helmi et al. (2018). They examined the motions of the nine ‘classical’ dwarf spheroidal galaxies (Fornax, Draco, Carina, Ursa Minor, Sextans, Leo I, Leo II, Sagittarius, Sculptor, and the ‘ultra-faint dwarf’ Boötes I), as well as 75 globular clusters. They identified a few hundred up to a few thousand members per dwarf system, and determined their distances with typical uncertainties of around 2–10 kpc. They noted suggestions of tidal streams in the case of Carina, and spatial asymmetries in the case of Fornax.

Most remarkable was the information on their derived orbits, which were reconstructed based on models of the Milky Way’s mass distribution. They found that Draco and Ursa Minor have very similar orbits, orthogonal to that of Sagittarius. Most are on (slightly) prograde orbits, while Fornax is retrograde, qualitatively similar to what was found for globular clusters. But their eccentricities are very different: few have very eccentric orbits, with Carina even being somewhat circular. They concluded that there is only limited similarity between the orbits of globular clusters and dwarf spheroidals. And that their eccentricity distribution was inconsistent with recent cosmological simulations. Their orbits also contrast with those of the ultra-faint dwarf galaxies, for which Gaia-based proper-motions suggested largely eccentric and retrograde trajectories (e.g., Simon, 2018; Patel et al., 2020; Cerny et al., 2023).

I gave more details on the planar distributions of the classical satellite galaxies of the Milky Way (the ‘Vast Polar Structure’) and of M31 (the ‘Great Plane of Andromeda’), their appearance in cosmological simulations, and the ‘plane of satellites’ problem, in essay 118.

AT A BASIC LEVEL, Gaia DR3 is being used to filter out foreground objects in other studies, resulting in cleaner membership, and more accurate distances. This has been applied to HST studies of Sculptor (Tran et al., 2022) and Fornax (Oakes et al., 2022). Combining HST and Gaia data also gave significantly improved proper motions for the faintest Gaia sources, e.g. in the case of Fornax and Draco (McKinnon et al., 2024).

IMPROVED GAIA POSITIONS and proper motions have been used to derive better orbits and orbital histories of a number of these Local Group dwarf spheroidals. These have led to improved insights into their orbital alignments, infall trajectories, and perturbative effects.

Amongst these, Casetti-Dinescu et al. (2022) made a combined HST–Gaia analysis of 2300 Leo I stars, confirming that its orbital pole is well aligned with that of the Vast Polar Structure (defined by the majority of the Milky Way’s brightest dSph satellites). Pace et al. (2022) used Gaia EDR3 to measure the bulk motion of 52 of the Milky Way’s dwarf spheroidal galaxies. Of 46 with known line-of-sight velocities they identified six (Car II, Car III, Hor I, Hyi I, Phx II, and Ret II) as likely LMC satellites.

THE GAIA proper motions are also being used to probe their structure, internal kinematics, and bulk rotation. For Sagittarius, Ferguson & Strigari (2020) inferred a triaxial shape with axis ratios 1 : 0.76 : 0.43. From 120 000 members in its core, del Pino et al. (2021) identified a 2.5 kpc-long bar, tidal tails (the Sgr stream, essay 198), a main body strongly sheared by tidal forces, and an inner core, of dimension $500 \times 330 \times 300 \text{ pc}^3$, rotating at $4.13 \pm 0.16 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Other models have been presented for Draco (Massari et al., 2020), Sextans (Tokiwa et al., 2023), and for Carina, Draco, Fornax, Sculptor, Sextans and Ursa Minor (Martínez-García et al., 2023). Significant bulk rotation has also been found in Carina, Fornax, and Sculptor (Martínez-García et al., 2021).

THE DERIVED orbits have remarkable consequences for understanding star formation and gas dissipation in these old stellar populations. The present assumption is that their gas-rich progenitors lost their gas during their infall into the Milky Way halo of order 10 Gyr ago. Star formation at the time is believed to have occurred as a result of ram pressure of their gas content, before its removal by the hot Galactic corona.

Observational verification requires accurate orbits and infall times, viz. when the galaxy first comes within the halo’s growing virial radius (Yang et al., 2024). From the orbits of eight of the classical dwarf spheroidals (Carina, Draco, Fornax, Leo I, Leo II, Sculptor, Sextans, and Ursa Minor), as well as eight ultra-faint dwarf galaxies, Miyoshi & Chiba (2020) showed that the satellite’s infall time agrees with the epoch of maximum star-formation, specifically as derived from HST colour–magnitude diagrams (Weisz et al., 2014).

In contrast to their typical ages of around 8–10 Gyr, Yang et al. (2024) reported a small population of young (~1 Gyr old) intermediate-mass ($1.8 - 3 M_{\odot}$) stars in several of the Milky Way’s dwarf spheroidals, including Sculptor, Ursa Minor and Sextans. They associate the birth of these young stars with the epoch when their gas-rich progenitors entered our Galaxy’s halo and corona.

The detailed effects of tidal and ram-pressure stripping have been modelled in a number of systems: in Fornax (Borukhovetskaya et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022; Di Cintio et al., 2024), in Leo I (Pacucci et al., 2023), in Draco (Grønnow et al., 2024), in Sculptor (Tolstoy et al., 2023), and in a number of others (Qi et al., 2022). Other modelling is leading to possible implications for their origin and dark matter content (Hammer et al., 2020; Pozo et al., 2022; Guerra et al., 2023; Andrade et al., 2024).

GLOBULAR CLUSTERS hold important clues about their history and tidal disruption (e.g. Rostami Shirazi et al., 2022). For Sagittarius, and in addition to its previously-known globular clusters (NGC 6715, Arp 2, Terzan 7, and Terzan 8 in the main body, and Pal 12, Whiting 1, NGC 2419, NGC 4147, and NGC 5634 in the extended tidal streams), Garro et al. (2021) used VISTA–VVV and Gaia EDR3 to identify 21 new clusters, 17 metal-rich and 4 metal-poor. With their own evolution controlled by the combined potential of both Sagittarius itself and the Milky Way, Kundu et al. (2022) used Gaia EDR3 to identify extra-tidal candidates, attributing their distribution to the dominant effect of Sagittarius itself. I said more on these globular clusters, and the relationship between Sagittarius and its nuclear star cluster, M54, in essay 198 on the Sagittarius stream.

The Fornax dwarf spheroidal has six associated globular clusters. The most recent, found in DECam imaging, and experiencing tidal destruction, is also seen as an overdensity in the Gaia data (Wang et al., 2019).

To identify the possible globular cluster progenitors, Boldrini & Bovy (2022) propagated the Gaia-based orbits of 170 Milky Way clusters, and its known satellite galaxies, backwards in time for 11 Gyr. None show clear association with any of the eight classical dwarf spheroidal galaxies, even though a large fraction of them are believed to have been accreted. They concluded that the globular clusters were either accreted as part of now-disrupted satellite galaxies, or that they may have had dark matter haloes in the past, affecting their orbits.

GAIA POSITIONS and space motions have assigned a number of high velocity and hypervelocity stars as originating from the Sagittarius dwarf. The first two were discovered with Gaia DR2, and originated 20–40 Myr ago (Montanari et al., 2019). The third, J1443+1453, at heliocentric distance $2.90_{-0.48}^{+0.72}$ kpc and space velocity $\sim 500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, was similarly found (from Gaia DR2) to intersect with its orbit $37.8_{-6.0}^{+4.6}$ Myr ago, close to its latest pericentric passage through the Milky Way (Huang et al., 2021). With Gaia EDR3, a further 60 Galactic high-velocity stars, including two hypervelocity stars, were inferred to have been tidally stripped from it, also at pericentre (Li et al., 2022). These associations are further supported by their similar metallicities (Li et al., 2023).